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DUAL SYSTEM TEACHING OF ENGLISH

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Annotation: *The main content of this article is that higher education English teachers provide recommendations and methods on how to help students learn English in ability-based classes and how to improve their knowledge. In addition, this article explores effective methods of teaching English in mixed classrooms.*

Key words: *dual education, upper classes, classroom communication, classification dynamics, classroom assignments, communicative language.*

Аннотация: *Основное содержание данной статьи заключается в том, что преподаватели английского языка в высших учебных заведениях предоставляют рекомендации и методы, как помочь студентам изучать английский язык на занятиях, основанных на способностях, и как улучшить свои знания. Кроме того, в данной статье исследуются эффективные методы преподавания английского языка в смешанных классах.*

Ключевые слова: *дуальное образование, старшие классы, классное общение, классификационная динамика, классные задания, коммуникативный язык.*

INTRODUCTION

Classes with large differences in ability, motivation for learning English, needs, interests, educational background, learning styles, anxieties, experiences, and other factors are known as mixed-ability classes. Teaching a group of students with distinctly varying levels of language proficiency is quite challenging. They may have varied English proficiency levels from the outset or learn the language at very different rates. This is a very typical issue.

LITERATURE REVIEW AND METHODOLOGY

Very frequently, the instructor must figure out how to address the demands of a class that has two or more clearly differentiated levels of ability. Naturally, there are no simple answers to this dilemma, thus it would be incorrect to pretend that there are any.

The class should be informed about the problem and told that it is something that the entire class must cope with. This is an important first step. Most effectively, this should be conducted in the pupils' native language. It is crucial to emphasize the value of collaboration among the class members and the requirement that they utilize English whenever feasible in classroom discussion because the majority of solutions to problems require their participation.

If you want to include every student in the class, pair and group work are crucial. The utilization of surveys and interviews is a key strategy here. You may ensure that every student participates to the fullest by partnering up weaker and stronger students and including them in the development and administration of the questionnaire. The stronger pupils can then interview the weaker ones, and vice versa. Naturally, this may frustrate the stronger individuals, but if they are able to view their position as one of "helper" or even mentor, it may also have a good impact.

Project work is a second activity that can be fruitful in mixed ability classrooms. Another technique is to establish groups that are around the same level and assign various tasks that are appropriate to each group's level. This may also be done successfully utilizing mixed groups where the stronger support the weaker. You may give each group a task that it can do effectively by altering the assignment's difficulty, giving the more capable pupils the right amount of challenge without demotivating the less capable ones.

Homework makes up a third category. No of the level, if you assign the identical homework to the entire class, you can anticipate extremely inconsistent outcomes. Similar to progress exams, homework should serve to reinforce what students have learned in class. To this purpose, assigning easier assignments to less capable pupils can aid in both motivating them and providing them more experience in language-related skills they have not yet mastered.

The stronger pupils in the group should be given more difficult assignments to complete in order to keep them engaged and moving forward. Although it requires the instructor to do more effort, the end result ought to be results. Drilling with the choir is a good approach to engage timid or underachieving youngsters. It may provide good practice in rhythm and intonation, as well as reinforcing word order and grammatical structure, if used sparingly (i.e., not all the time). Finally, use tact while you're asking

questions. By choosing weaker students to be the first to respond to a question in open class, try to avoid putting them "on the spot." Instead, make an effort to foster a culture of attentive listening in the classroom by asking a better student a question before asking a weaker student to repeat it. This type of contact may take some getting used to, but once it does, it may be highly beneficial for class dynamics. In conclusion, there is some degree of mixed ability in all courses. Extreme situations, when near native speakers are mixed with novices, can be quite difficult for the teacher.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In these situations, it's crucial to keep in mind that all of your students will learn something from the lesson, if perhaps not exactly what you intended to teach them or the same thing. For instance, the weaker students may start to be able to employ a new tense, while the novices may start to understand your classroom language.

Mixed levels are inherently problematic. It might be challenging to teach pupils who have varying levels of learning. However, teachers may deliver content in a way that will simultaneously engage all students on all levels by learning to discern learning capacities.

They may have varying initial English proficiency levels, or this may occur for a variety of reasons, but mostly due to various learning preferences, learning rates, degrees of desire, and, very frequently, logistical considerations.

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It is crucial to emphasize the importance of teamwork and for the class to use English whenever feasible in classroom communication because the majority of the solutions to the issue depend on cooperation between the class members. Here are some methods teachers can use to instruct a group of pupils with various learning styles. These are a few approaches a teacher can use to handle this circumstance.

1. Supportive Learning Environment. It's critical to provide a positive learning atmosphere in the classroom where students feel comfortable and able to give their best effort. The term "learning environment" simply refers to the classroom setting and how students interact with it. No of their learning styles, teachers must design a classroom that will benefit all of their pupils. If in-class tasks are required, for instance, create a basic list of prerequisites and then provide students with supplementary instructions on a case-by-case basis to meet their learning styles. Make sure the classroom has areas where kids may focus and concentrate in peace. Or offer them the chance to collaborate with others. Ensure that the class is aware that the alternatives are available since every student performs best in a different environment.

2. Needs assessment. Use a needs analysis to urge the students to consider their learning preferences, linguistic requirements, learning techniques, love of learning, drive, and language strengths and limitations. What types of classroom activities do you enjoy or benefit from, for example? Which linguistic ability do you most want to hone? Do you like working alone or with a partner better? Would you want to work in a group throughout the session or just sit and listen to the teacher? In pairs or small groups, students compare their solutions. You should gather the data and provide a statistical breakdown of the main inquiries and responses. This will support the growth of the class's feeling of collective community.

3. Teamwork. Use a variety of engagement styles in the classroom. Students should collaborate in teams, couples, and independently. Groupings must be switched up often to provide students a chance to interact with other students. It will be easier to accommodate the range of levels in the class if students' work in the class is varied. There is a chance that these groupings will have comparable or mixed levels. In a smaller group, it is hoped that the weaker student would feel more capable of contributing. Divide the information among the pupils if the group is working with a certain set of facts, pushing them to cooperate. Consider assigning various levels or quantities of work to each group by splitting your class into levels for the duration of the course. The class's discussion of this tactic should aid in preventing stigmatization.

4. Work in pairs. Strong and weak can be paired, as well as strong and weak. Perhaps the strong with the weak will function nicely in a carefully restricted activity. Perhaps using strong with strong will be advantageous in a more liberated action. Here, variety in the pairings is vital, and you should also pay attention to the connections in general.

5. The entire class mingle. This is one of my preferred approaches.

During a mingle exercise, students must converse or engage with a large number of different classmates quickly in order to complete a task. This implies that every student will interact with students who are working at varying levels and will have greater and worse communication. This helps the less capable kids and gives the more capable ones opportunity.

6. Giving Different Students Different Instruction.

Because of the input of the more accomplished students, the average and lower performing students are encouraged to attempt and expand their knowledge. Teachers may adapt to a wide range of diverse interests, cultural backgrounds, and global knowledge by using differentiated education, which leads to more engaging classroom engagement. Setting the stage for the acceptance of diversity begins with the mindset of the instructor.

7.Process. Process refers to how students interact with and absorb material. This is crucial because it gives pupils the chance to give new information time to fully sink in. Students get the chance to assess what they may or may not comprehend via the process. Teachers can monitor and evaluate a student's development using this procedure. For instance, John McCarthy, an educational consultant, advises instructors to create "one or two processing experiences for every 30 minutes of instruction." Through these interactions, both students and teachers may take a break and determine who requires extra education and who does not.

8.Products. Products are tasks or projects that motivate students to apply knowledge in both inside- and outside-the-classroom contexts. For instance, when the material has been covered and students have had time to comprehend it, encourage them to create a project of their own that best demonstrates what they have learned. For instance, smaller kids can produce a poster board with images and labeling, while older students might write a little play or draw illustrations. Teachers might wish to provide pupils with a menu of possibilities and even let them work in groups.

CONCLUSION

In my conclusion, be courteous in your questioning strategies. By choosing weaker students to be the first to respond to a question in open class, try to avoid putting them "on the spot." Instead, make an effort to foster a culture of attentive listening in the classroom by asking a better student a question before asking a weaker student to repeat it. This type of contact may take some getting used to, but once it does, it may be highly beneficial for class dynamics. If you only teach a few more differentiated lessons, even the teacher could find it enjoyable. Dare to be different, and you never know what you could discover. Be honest, and display your vitality and excitement!

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